

The Role of Phosphates in the Oxidation of Glucose.

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The oxidation of glucose is one of the most important chemical changes of the organism taking place at constant temperature and nearly constant alkalinity. An almost neutral phosphate mixture is known to be a constituent of many living organisms and this accounts for the maintenance of constant alkalinity. While constant alkalinity may be a determining factor, it is of importance to ascertain if phosphates by themselves exert any specific catalytic effect in the oxidation process. Lob (*Biochem. Zeit.*, 1911, 32, 43 and subsequent papers), Witzemann (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1920, 45, 1) and Harden and Henley (*Biochem. J.*, 1921, 15, 672) have studied the oxidation of glucose by hydrogen peroxide in the presence of phosphates. Witzemann found that disodium phosphate exerted a catalytic effect, for he found that even at constant alkalinity, the rate of oxidation was dependent upon the amount of disodium phosphates present in the reaction mixture. He was not able to say definitely whether any intermediate complex between the hexose and phosphate was responsible for the increased rate of oxidation; but he found a parallelism to exist between the rate of decomposition of hydrogen peroxide in the phosphate mixtures and the rate of oxidation of glucose in the same phosphate mixtures. He suggested that a $\text{Na}_2\text{HPO}_4 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ complex might exist in solution and this might be the cause of the increased rate of oxidation. This observation, if correct, is of very great importance. The conclusion that can be drawn from Witzemann's results that phosphates do exert a catalytic effect in addition to playing the part of buffer mixtures is in partial agreement with the views of Lob, while Harden and Henley opine that the only part played by the phosphates is the regulation of alkalinity.

If both glucose and hydrogen peroxide form complexes in solution with phosphates, the problem of investigating the nature of such complexes becomes difficult in a mixture of these three substances. It occurred to the writer that some light may be thrown on the

problem, by studying firstly the rate of oxidation of glucose with an oxidising agent satisfying the following conditions: (1) It should not ordinarily react with glucose in acid or neutral solutions. (2) It should be able to oxidise glucose in alkaline solutions and in particular at small concentrations of OH ions as can be obtained by using phosphate buffer mixtures. (3) It should not be such as would form any kind of complex with phosphates. Iodine was found to satisfy all these conditions. A study of the kinetics of oxidation of glucose by such an oxidising agent in the presence of phosphate buffer mixtures should at once enable us to determine with a certain amount of definiteness whether or not a hexose-phosphate complex comes into existence and enhances the rate of oxidation. Secondly a revision of the rate of decomposition of hydrogen peroxide in phosphate mixtures was thought necessary to see if Witzemann's observation about the complex formation could be confirmed.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Oxidation of Glucose by Iodine.

As stated above, iodine does not react with glucose in neutral and acid solutions, even on heating for several hours. It was therefore thought necessary first of all to determine the amount of iodine necessary to oxidise one molecule of glucose. A few initial experiments showed that the reaction takes place with measurable speed in phosphate buffer mixtures. Experiments carried on in buffer mixtures having pH values between 7 and 8 showed that in all cases one molecule of iodine was taken up by one molecule of glucose, showing thereby that the oxidation progresses only to the stage of gluconic acid, just as in the case of oxidation with bromine (Bunzel and Mathews, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, **31**, 464).

All the experiments described in what follows were carried out at a constant temperature (22°). The sample of glucose used was Merck's extra pure anhydrous powder. Care was taken to purify the disodium and monosodium phosphates by recrystallisation. The reaction was followed by titrating a known amount of the reaction mixture with standard sodium thiosulphate solution.

Initial experiments on velocity measurements showed that the reaction does not proceed smoothly like one of the second order. Figures given in Table I indicate that the velocity constant falls very rapidly as the reaction proceeds.

TABLE I.

20 c. c. of Na HPO₄ (0.33M)
 5 c. c. of NaH₂PO₄ (0.33M) in 100 c. c. of reaction mixture.

Time in min.	Conc. of I ₂ in mols. per litre.	Conc. of glucose in mols. per litre.	Bimol. K
0	0.0178	0.0817	—
10	0.0165	0.0804	9.361
20	0.0154	0.0793	8.999
40	0.0137	0.0776	8.221
100	0.0111	0.0750	5.685
200	0.00885	0.0728	4.554

Calculations showed that the data could not be made to fit into equations for reactions of higher orders. The fall in velocity constant should therefore be attributed to other causes. As the reaction progresses hydriodic acid and gluconic acids are formed and tend to reduce the alkalinity of the system. If the reaction is very sensitive to changes of p_H the fall in p_H may be one of the causes for the fall in velocity constant. Another factor tending to affect the velocity in the same direction is the formation and accumulation of iodide ions in the system; these remove a portion of the active iodine as I₃. This latter cause could be detected and remedied by starting with a pretty large initial concentration of an iodide in the reaction mixture thereby maintaining the concentrations of I ions practically constant throughout the reaction. Experiments were next made to see if the reaction proceeds in conformity with unimolecular law when the initial concentration of glucose was made very large compared to the concentration of iodine, the concentration of the iodide ions being maintained constant as suggested above. The figures in Table II indicate that even with this modification the unimolecular velocity constant gradually falls as the reaction proceeds.

TABLE II.

4.5 gms. glucose ; 4.15 gms. KI ;

20 c. c. of 0.33M Na_2HPO_4
5 c. c. of 0.33M NaH_2PO_4 made up to 100 c. c.

25 c. c. of iodine soln. (0.140N in 0.25N KI).

Time in min.	$\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$	K/2.3
0	21.65 c. c.	
10	20.90	0.00154
30	19.40	0.00151
60	17.60	0.00150
90	16.40	0.01330
120	15.40	0.001233
150	13.65	0.001113
300	11.50	0.000916
∞	0	

These figures further lead to the inference that the fall in velocity constant is not so much due to the formation of I_2 ions but mainly due to some other more powerful factor. An experiment made under the same conditions but with double the quantity of glucose showed that the time for half change in regard to the disappearance of iodine was exactly half as in the above experiment. This shows that the reaction is really unimolecular with respect to iodine. The above experiments were carried out at constant alkalinity with a phosphate buffer mixture ($p_{\text{H}} = 7.41$). If the reaction is really unimolecular with respect to iodine the only possible inference that could be drawn at this stage with regard to the fall in velocity constant appears to be that the reaction is extremely sensitive even to such small changes of p_{H} as can be brought about by the addition of very small quantities of acids to buffer mixtures. The validity of this inference should be tested by making velocity measurements at different degrees of alkalinity. Since the preparation of such buffer mixtures involves the use of disodium and monosodium phosphates

in varying proportions it was thought necessary at first to see if at the same p_H the velocity was in any way dependent on the concentration of either Na_2HPO_4 or NaH_2PO_4 .

Influence of the Concentration of Na_2HPO_4 .

Tables III-VI contain results of velocity measurements made with different concentrations of Na_2HPO_4 and NaH_2PO_4 at the same alkalinity. In all these experiments 100 c.c. of the reaction mixture contained 9 gms. of glucose, 4.15 gms. of KI, 25 c.c. of 0.15 N iodine soln. in 0.25 KI and different quantities of phosphates as mentioned in each table.

TABLE III.

40 C.c. 0.033 M Na_2HPO_4 ; 10 c.c. 0.33 M NaH_2PO_4

Time in min.	$Na_2S_2O_3$	K/2.3
0	21.6 c.c.	...
10	20.65	0.00280
20	19.20	0.00256
30	18.15	0.00252
60	15.80	0.00226
120	12.35	0.00203
∞	0	

TABLE IV.

20 C.c. 0.33 M Na_2HPO_4 ; 5 c.c. 0.33 M NaH_2PO_4

0	21.60	0.00291
10	20.20	0.00273
20	19.05	0.00257
40	17.05	0.00224
60	15.85	0.00185
120	12.95	
∞	0	

TABLE V.

15 C.c. 0.33 M Na_2HPO_4 ; 3.75 c.c. 0.33 M NaH_2PO_4

0	21.80	—
10	20.50	0.00267
20	19.55	0.00237
40	17.90	0.00220
60	16.65	0.00195
120	14.05	0.00169
180	12.30	0.00138
∞	0	

TABLE VI.

10 C.c. (0.33M) Na_2HPO_4 ; 2.5 c.c. (0.33 M) NaH_2PO_4

Time in min.	$\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$	$K/2.3$
0	21.80 c.c.	—
10	20.45	0.00278
20	19.45	0.00246
40	18.00	0.00210
60	16.95	0.00182
120	14.85	0.00139
∞	0	

It will be noticed that the velocity constants in all the above experiments in the first few minutes have almost the same value thereby indicating clearly that the amount of either of the phosphates has nothing to do with the rate of reaction so long as p_{H} remains the same. It is also to be seen that in mixtures having a greater amount of disodium phosphate the rate of fall of velocity constant is not so great as in mixtures having lesser amounts of disodium phosphate.

Experiments were now made to determine the variation of velocity with p_{H} . The concentrations of glucose, KI and iodine in all these experiments were kept the same as in the above experiments; only the amounts of phosphates were varied so as to produce different degrees of alkalinity. In Table VII are given the rates of reaction as measured in the first ten minutes in different mixtures.

TABLE VII.

p_{H}	K/2'3	p_{H}	K/2'3
7.0	0.000	7.6	0.0051
7.1	0.0008	7.8	0.0066
7.2	0.00179	8.0	0.0075
7.4	0.0029	...	...

These figures indicate that the reaction is very sensitive towards variation in p_{H} . The fact that in a phosphate mixture of $p_{\text{H}} = 7$ the reaction does not proceed at all, just as in a solution containing no phosphates is clear proof that phosphates by their mere presence cannot accelerate the oxidation of glucose. It is now easy to explain why on looking at Tables III-VI we find that the rate of fall of velocity constant at the same p_{H} is greater in mixtures containing lesser amounts of Na HPO_4 than in those containing greater amounts of it as the change in p_{H} for an addition of the same amount of acid to a solution containing a lesser amount of Na_2HPO_4 is greater than in the case of a solution containing a greater amount of the phosphate. It would therefore appear that the main factor determining the velocity of reaction is p_{H} and not the concentration of phosphates. We may conclude that phosphates do not form complexes in solution which get more easily oxidised than the free glucose molecule.

Decomposition of Hydrogen Peroxide in Phosphate Mixtures.

The decomposition of Merck's perhydrol in phosphate mixtures has been studied in the following experiments. In pure aqueous solutions this specimen of hydrogen peroxide was found to decompose at a slow but measurable rate at 60° , and the other velocity measurements were also made at this temperature. To 100 c.c. of either pure water or the phosphate buffer mixture 1 c.c. of Merck's perhydrol (18N) was added, 10 c.c. of the mixture pipetted out at different intervals, mixed with excess of dilute sulphuric acid and titrated against decinormal permanganate solution. In all

cases a small period of induction was observed before H_2O_2 began to decompose normally. This is in accordance with the observations of previous workers (Rice and Reiff, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1927, 31, 1953). Tables VIII and IX give data obtained in phosphate mixtures of $p_H = 7.6$ and $p_H = 7.8$ respectively.

TABLE VIII.

$p_H = 7.6$		
Time in min.	KMnO ₄	K (unimolecular)
0	18.00 c.c.	—
10	16.30 initial	—
20	13.60	0.00787
30	11.40	0.00776
40	9.55	0.00774
50	8.00	0.00774
60	6.85	0.00753
∞	0	

TABLE IX.

$p_H = 7.8$		
0	17.85	—
10	15.40 initial	—
20	12.25	0.00994
30	9.80	0.00981
40	7.80	0.00985
50	6.25	0.00980
60	5.20	0.00943
70	4.30	0.00923
∞	0	Mean 0.00968

Table X contains results obtained in a series of experiments carried out at constant alkalinity but with different amounts of phosphates.

TABLE X.

C.c. of phosphates in 100 c.c. of mixture.

0.33 M Na_2HPO_4	NaH_2PO_4	K
5 c.c.	1.25 c.c.	0.006728
10	2.5	0.006714
15	3.75	0.006745
20	5.0	0.006792
40	10.00	<u>0.006890</u>
	Mean	0.006790

It is obvious from the table that the amount of disodium or dihydrogen phosphate does not matter at the same p_{H} . Table XI gives the velocity constants obtained in solutions of different degrees of alkalinity.

TABLE XI.

p_{H} of phosphate mixtures.	K
7.0	0.00060
7.20	0.00407
7.40	0.00678
7.60	0.00773
7.80	0.00968
8.00	0.01200
Pure water	0.00056

It will be noticed that the rates of decomposition in pure water and phosphate mixtures of $p_{\text{H}} = 7$ are almost identical. The results in this table show that the rate of decomposition is simply proportional to p_{H} ; we are therefore led to the conclusion that no phosphate-hydrogen peroxide complex could exist in solution.

Summary.

The kinetics of the reaction between glucose and iodine in phosphate buffer mixtures has been studied at 22°. At constant alkalinity the rate of oxidation has been found to be independent of the amounts of phosphates present in the mixture.

The rate of reaction has been found to increase with increase in p_H . In neutral solutions and in a phosphate buffer mixture of $p_H = 7.0$ the reaction does not proceed at all. These results indicate that no hexose-phosphate complex is formed in solution. The only part played by phosphates is the regulation of constant alkalinity.

Velocity of decomposition of hydrogen peroxide in water and in phosphate buffer mixtures has been studied at 60°. The results obtained lead to the conclusion that no phosphate-hydrogen peroxide complex is formed in solution. The velocity of decomposition increases with increase in p_H ; at constant alkalinity the amounts of phosphates present have no influence on this velocity.

Further work on the problem will be reported in a later communication.

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